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Detailed open-source documentation including elements used in the
characterisation setup

Practical Guidelines for Thin Film PV Researchers

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Abstract

This document is addressed to Photovoltaic (PV) researchers interested to investigate their devices for visual synapses and neuromorphic applications. It is written as part of the Marie Curie Staff Exchange project SOLIS <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101183049>. The document provides guidelines for establishing an experimental platform to characterise artificial synapses using optical or electrical stimulation. Designed for thin film photovoltaic researchers, it covers hardware configurations, synchronisation strategies, and standardised measurement protocols for synaptic plasticity characterisation.

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1 Introduction

Visual synapses operate through optically-controlled memristive behavior, leveraging persistent photoconductivity in thin film semiconductors. Characterisation requires:

- Pulsed optical stimulation (write operation)
- Electrical conductance readout (read operation)
- Precise temporal control (ms to s timescales)
- Synchronized triggering between stimulation and measurement

This guide addresses two primary hardware configurations: dual-channel Source meter units (e.g., Keithley 2636A) and combined waveform generator + measurement instrument setups.

Scope of This Document

This guide covers **both electrical and visual/optical synapse** characterisation:

- **Electrical synapses:** Electrical voltage or current pulses are applied directly to the device (memristors, ReRAM, phase-change memory)
- **Visual/optical synapses:** Optical pulses from an LED are used to stimulate the device (photovoltaic devices, photodetectors, persistent photoconductors)

Both approaches share similar measurement principles but differ only in the way the stimulus is delivered.

1.1 Key Differences from Sourcemeter Approach

- **Sourcemeter:** Integrated source and measure capabilities on two independent channels with computer control. Makes things easier.
- **AWG + DMM:** Separated sourcing (AWG) and measurement (DMM) functions
- **Challenge:** Only the DMM is computer-controlled; the AWG must be pre-configured
- **Solution:** Design AWG waveforms on both channels that include all necessary stimulus and read phases, then trigger DMM measurements at precise times to read the current, and therefore the conductivity.

2 Hardware Configurations

2.1 Configuration A: Dual-Channel Source meter (Keithley 2636A)

Required equipment:

- Keithley 2636A (or equivalent dual-channel SMU)
- Fiber-coupled LED with driver
- LED driver with external trigger capability
- Optical fiber and collimator
- Calibrated optical power meter

Connection scheme:

- **Channel A:** Device terminals (apply read voltage, measure current)
- **Channel B:** LED driver trigger input (pulse generation)
- **Optical path:** LED → fiber → collimator → device

Advantages: Integrated control, high timing precision, simplified synchronisation via software.

2.2 Configuration B: Waveform Generator + Measurement Instrument

Required equipment:

- Dual-channel waveform generator (e.g., Multicom Pro MP751062)
- Digital multimeter with trigger input (e.g., Keysight 34460A) or single-channel SMU
- Fiber-coupled LED with triggered driver (e.g., Thorlabs LEDD1B + M430F1)
- Multimode optical fiber and collimator
- Calibrated optical power meter

Connection scheme:

- **WFG Channel 1:** LED driver external trigger input (optical stimulation pulses)
- **WFG Channel 2:** Device bias (apply read voltage V_{read})
- **DMM input:** Device current measurement
- **Trigger synchronisation:** WFG output \rightarrow DMM external trigger input

Critical consideration: The measurement instrument must support external triggering to synchronize current acquisition with the pulse sequence.

2.3 Measurement Using a Shunt Resistor

Although most DMMs can directly measure current, we recommend to operate the DMM in voltage mode and the device current should be calculated from the voltage drop across a known shunt resistor R_{sh} . This configuration offers several advantages. First, it provides a well-defined and reproducible transimpedance conversion, whereas the internal shunt of the DMM in current mode is range-dependent and not precisely specified. Second, voltage-mode measurements show a higher bandwidth and lower noise, which is essential for time-resolved experiments such as pulse-induced synaptic plasticity or transient photoconductivity. Third, the external resistor allows independent optimisation of the measurement sensitivity and bias stability, since the burden voltage ($I_{\text{device}}R_{\text{sh}}$) can be selected to remain much smaller than the applied bias. Overall, the use of a calibrated external shunt resistor is better for accurate, high-speed, and bias-stable current measurements in pulsed optoelectronic characterisation.

2.3.1 Circuit Topology: Electrical Synapse

Electrical Synapse Configuration:

Measurement Principle – Electrical

- AWG Channel 1 applies stimulus voltage $V_{stim}(t)$ or current $I_{stim}(t)$
- AWG Channel 2 applies read voltage V_{read} (typically 0.1–0.2 V)
- Current through device: $I = \frac{V_{shunt}}{R_{shunt}}$
- Device conductance: $G = \frac{I}{V_{read}}$
- DMM measures voltage across shunt resistor

2.3.2 Circuit Topology: Visual Synapse

Visual Synapse Configuration:

Measurement Principle – Visual

- AWG Channel 1 generates TTL pulse to trigger LED driver
- LED produces optical pulse → illuminates device
- AWG Channel 2 applies read voltage V_{read} (typically 0.1–0.2 V)
- Photocurrent through device: $I_{ph} = \frac{V_{shunt}}{R_{shunt}}$
- Device photoconductance: $G_{ph} = \frac{I_{ph}}{V_{read}}$
- DMM measures voltage across shunt resistor (or direct current if shunt omitted)

2.3.3 Selecting the Shunt Resistor

Choose R_{shunt} based on expected device current range:

$$R_{shunt} = \frac{V_{DMM,max}}{I_{device,max} \times 1.5} \quad (1)$$

Example: For a device with expected maximum current of $100 \mu A$:

$$R_{shunt} = \frac{10 \text{ V}}{100 \mu A \times 1.5} = 67 \text{ k}\Omega \Rightarrow \text{Use } 68 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (2)$$

Typical values by device type:

-
- Memristors (oxide-based): 10–100 k Ω
 - Visual synapses (low photocurrent): 100 k Ω –1 M Ω
 - Phase-change memory: 1–10 k Ω

2.4 Detailed Hardware Requirements

2.4.1 Common Equipment (Both Electrical and Visual)

1. Dual-channel arbitrary waveform generator with:
 - Independent channel control
 - Capability to output DC + pulsed waveforms
 - Typical voltage range: ± 10 V minimum, but we will use less than 5V in most cases.
 - Output impedance: 50 Ω (typical for this kind of instrument)
 - TTL trigger output capability (for LED triggering)
2. Keysight 34461A Digital Multimeter, or equivalent with:
 - Computer interface (USB/GPIB/LAN)
 - High-speed sampling capability is preferred
 - Good resolution especially for current measurement: 6.5 digits
3. Connection hardware:
 - BNC cables
 - Banana-to-BNC adapters
 - Probe station

2.4.2 Additional Equipment for Electrical Synapses

- Precision shunt resistor (R_{shunt}):
 - Value: 100 Ω to 10 k Ω (device-dependent)
 - Tolerance: $\pm 0.1\%$ or better
 - Power rating: depends on the expected currents

2.4.3 Additional Equipment for Visual Synapses

- Fibre-coupled LED with external trigger capability:
 - Wavelengths: 365–1500 nm (select based on your device absorption, or possible subgap transitions)
 - Optical power: 1–50 mW (fibre-coupled)
 - Recommended: Thorlabs M430F1, M530F1, M625F1, M850F1
 - Cost per LED: €200–350
- LED driver with external trigger:
 - External trigger input (TTL, 3.3–5 V)

-
- Trigger-to-output delay: $< 1 \mu\text{s}$
 - Constant current drive mode
 - Recommended: Thorlabs LEDD1B T-Cube
 - Cost: €280–350
 - Optical components:
 - Multimode optical fibre (200–600 μm core diameter)
 - SMA or FC/PC connectors
 - Collimator/focusing optics (focal length 11–25 mm)
 - Cost: €100–200
 - Calibrated optical power metre:
 - Si photodiode detector (350–1100 nm)
 - Power range: 1 nW to 100 mW
 - Calibration certificate (traceable)
 - Cost: €400–1200

2.5 Budget Estimates

2.5.1 Budget-Conscious Visual Synapse Setup (\sim €2,350)

Component	Model/Specs	Cost (€)
Waveform generator	Multicomp Pro MP751062 (2-ch, 60 MHz)	250
Digital multimeter	Keysight 34460A (6.5-digit, triggerable)	1,300
Fiber-coupled LED	Thorlabs M430F1 (430 nm, 5.3 mW)	250
LED driver	Thorlabs LEDD1B (T-Cube, ext. trigger)	350
Optical components	Fiber + collimator	200
Total		2,350

Table 1: Low-cost experimental setup for visual synapse characterisation

Note: Multiple LEDs at different wavelengths are recommended to study spectral response.

2.5.2 Budget Breakdown: Electrical vs Visual

Component	Electrical	Visual
Waveform generator (2-ch)	€200–300	€200–300
Digital multimeter (triggerable)	€1000–1300	€1000–1300
Shunt resistor	€5–20	€5–20
LED + fibre	–	€200–250
LED driver (triggered)	–	€280–350
Optical power metre	–	€400–1200
Optical components	–	€100–200
Total	€1200–1650	€2200–3650

Table 2: Estimated equipment costs (2025)

3 Optical Calibration

3.1 Power Calibration Protocol

Accurate characterisation requires calibrated incident optical power density at the device surface.

Procedure:

1. Position optical power meter detector at device plane.
2. Measure optical power P_{opt} [mW] for each LED at operating current.
3. Calculate power density: $P_d = P_{\text{opt}}/A_{\text{beam}}$ [mW cm⁻²]
4. Record beam diameter at device position (measure spot size with beam profiler or imaging).
5. Verify spatial uniformity across device active area.

Requirements:

- Calibrated Si or InGaAs photodiode detector (wavelength-dependent)
- Power meter with nW to mW range
- Document: λ , P_{opt} , A_{beam} , LED current, measurement distance

4 Timing and Synchronisation

4.1 Temporal Parameters

Synaptic characterisation in thin film device should happen on timescales from milliseconds to seconds. Ideally we would go faster, but for the equipment described here, this is the fastest we can hope for:

$$T_{\text{period}} \geq t_{\text{pulse}} + t_{\text{delay}} + t_{\text{settle}} + t_{\text{meas}} \quad (3)$$

$$t_{\text{pulse}} : \text{optical stimulation duration (10–1000 ms)} \quad (4)$$

$$t_{\text{delay}} : \text{post-pulse relaxation (5–100 ms)} \quad (5)$$

$$t_{\text{settle}} : \text{measurement stabilization (2–20 ms)} \quad (6)$$

$$t_{\text{meas}} : \text{current acquisition window (1–50 ms)} \quad (7)$$

Ideally, we would go below the ms, but it is nearly impossible with standard DMMs.

4.2 Configuration A: Keithley 2636A Synchronisation

Synchronisation is managed internally via the controlling software:

1. Channel B outputs voltage pulse to trigger LED driver.
2. Software waits $t_{\text{pulse}} + t_{\text{delay}}$.
3. Channel A applies V_{read} , waits t_{settle} .
4. Channel A measures current.
5. Software calculates conductance: $G = I/V_{\text{read}}$.

NPLC setting: Use $\text{NPLC} = 0.1\text{--}1$ for balance between speed and noise rejection (see Section 5).

4.3 Configuration B: AWG + DMM Setup

Requires explicit hardware synchronisation. The general measurement sequence is:

for each pulse:

```
t=0:      WFG Ch1 triggers LED (ON for t_pulse)
t=t_pulse: LED turns OFF
t=t_pulse + t_delay: WFG triggers DMM acquisition
t=t_pulse + t_delay + t_settle: DMM samples current
Record I, calculate  $G = I / V_{\text{read}}$ 
```

Critical: Verify DMM trigger latency (typically 1–5 ms). Adjust t_{delay} accordingly.

Step 1: Configure AWG Channel 1

For Electrical Synapses (Stimulus):

1. Set waveform type: **Pulse/Square wave**
2. Set amplitude: V_{stim} (typically ± 1.0 to ± 2.0 V)
3. Set pulse width: t_{width} (typically 10–100 ms)
4. Set period: t_{period} (typically 100–200 ms)
5. Set number of cycles: N_{pulses} (typically 20–100)
6. Set offset: 0 V
7. Set burst mode: ON (to generate finite pulse train)
8. Output impedance: High-Z or 50 Ω . Usually it is ok to leave this parameter by default

For Visual Synapses (LED Trigger):

1. Set waveform type: **Pulse/Square wave**
2. Set amplitude: 3.3–5 V (TTL level for LED driver)
3. Set pulse width: t_{pulse} (typically 10–500 ms, LED illumination time)
4. Set period: t_{period} (typically 50–1000 ms)
5. Set number of cycles: N_{pulses} (typically 20–200)
6. Set offset: 0 V (produces 0 V to V_{TTL} pulses)
7. Set burst mode: ON
8. Output impedance: 50 Ω (for driving LED trigger input)

Step 2: Configure AWG Channel 2 (Read Voltage)

1. Set waveform type: **DC**
2. Set amplitude: $V_{\text{read}} = 0.1$ V (constant). We can go to higher read voltages, but we have to ensure that the read voltage does not act as a significant stimulus.
3. Alternatively, set to GND (0 V) if measuring photovoltaic devices in zero-bias mode. But in this case, you can get away with a single channel and just measure the photocurrent at each excitation.
4. Output: Continuous

Step 3: Configure Keysight 34461A

SCPI Commands for Computer Control:

```
*RST // Reset to defaults
CONF:VOLT:DC 10,MAX // DC voltage, 10V range, max resolution
VOLT:DC:NPLC 0.1 // Fast integration (0.1 PLC). Or less even
TRIG:SOUR IMM // Immediate trigger
TRIG:COUN N_pulses // Number of measurements
SAMP:COUN 1 // One sample per trigger
```

Step 4: Synchronised Measurement Procedure

Manual Synchronisation (No Computer):

1. Start AWG burst manually
2. Manually record DMM reading after each pulse
3. Repeat for all pulses
4. Calculate: $G_n = \frac{V_{\text{DMM},n}}{R_{\text{shunt}} \times V_{\text{read}}}$

Computer-Controlled Acquisition (Preferred):

1. **Pre-calculation:** Determine measurement times

$$t_{\text{measure},n} = n \times t_{\text{period}} + t_{\text{width}} + t_{\text{delay}} \quad (8)$$

where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{pulses}} - 1$

2. **Initialise DMM:** Send configuration via USB/GPIB
3. **Start AWG:** Trigger burst mode
4. **Timed measurements:** Query DMM at each $t_{\text{measure},n}$
5. **Data storage:** Save raw voltages, timestamps, and calculated conductances to CSV

4.4 Python Example Code (Configuration B)

```
import pyvisa
import time
import numpy as np

rm = pyvisa.ResourceManager()
dmm = rm.open_resource('USB0::0x0957::0x1798::MY12345678::INSTR')

# Configuration
dmm.write('*RST')
dmm.write('CONF:VOLT:DC 10,MAX')
dmm.write('VOLT:DC:NPLC 0.1')
```

```
measurements = []
t_period = 0.2 # 200 ms
t_width = 0.1 # 100 ms
t_delay = 0.01 # 10 ms
N_pulses = 50
R_shunt = 10000 # 10 kOhm
V_read = 0.1 # 100 mV

# Trigger AWG burst (manual or external trigger)
input("Press Enter after starting AWG burst...")

t_start = time.time()

for n in range(N_pulses):
    # Calculate when to measure
    t_target = t_start + n * t_period + t_width + t_delay

    # Wait until target time
    while time.time() < t_target:
        time.sleep(0.001) # 1 ms sleep

    # Measure
    voltage = float(dmm.query('READ?'))
    timestamp = time.time() - t_start
    I = voltage / R_shunt
    G = I / V_read
    measurements.append((n, timestamp, voltage, I, G))
    print(f"Pulse {n}: G = {G*1e6:.2f} uS")

# Save to CSV
np.savetxt('synapse_data.csv', measurements, delimiter=',',
           header='pulse,time_s,V_DMM,I_A,G_S', comments='')
```

4.5 Alternative: AWG with Trigger Output

If your AWG has a trigger/sync output:

1. Configure AWG to output trigger pulse at end of each stimulus pulse
2. Connect trigger output to DMM external trigger input
3. Configure DMM for external trigger:

```
TRIG:SOUR EXT // External trigger
TRIG:COUN N_pulses // Number of measurements
```

4. Start DMM acquisition, then start AWG burst
5. Retrieve all measurements after sequence completes:

```
dmm.write('INIT') // Start waiting for triggers
```

```
# Start AWG burst
time.sleep(N_pulses * t_period + 1) // Wait for completion
data = dmm.query('FETC?') // Retrieve all measurements
```

4.6 Instrument Speed Considerations

- **WFG:** Typical trigger jitter < 1 μ s, adequate for ms-scale pulses.
- **DMM (e.g., Keysight 34460A):** Integration time depends on NPLC; trigger delay \sim 2 ms. Use fast trigger mode if available.
- **Keithley 2636A:** Buffer-based acquisition with \sim 17 ms per point at NPLC=1 (60 Hz line frequency). Use lower NPLC for faster measurements. However, from my experience, it is better to read cadence to \gtrsim 30 ms per point for stability unless device currents at your chosen V_{read} are large enough (that is \gg 100 nA) to permit shorter integration times without excessive noise.
- **LED driver:** Rise/fall time typically < 1 μ s. Verify driver specifications but it is normally not a limitation.

5 Integration Time and Noise (NPLC)

The Number of Power Line Cycles (NPLC) controls integration time and noise rejection:

NPLC	Integration Time (60 Hz)	Application
0.01	0.17 ms	Fast transients, high noise
0.1	1.7 ms	Synapse readout, moderate noise
1.0	17 ms	Standard DC measurements
10	170 ms	Ultra-low noise, slow dynamics

Table 3: NPLC selection guidelines

Recommendation: For synaptic characterisation with $t_{\text{pulse}} \geq 10$ ms, use NPLC = 0.1–1.

5.1 Autorange vs Fixed Range

- **Autorange:** Instrument automatically selects current range. Use for wide current range devices or initial characterisation. Increases measurement time by \sim 2–5 \times .
- **Fixed Range:** Manual range selection. Use for well-characterised devices with known current levels. Fastest measurement speed.

5.2 4-Wire vs 2-Wire Sensing

- **4-Wire (Kelvin):** Eliminates lead resistance. Essential for low-resistance devices (< 100 Ω) and high-current measurements.
- **2-Wire:** Simpler configuration. Acceptable for high-resistance devices (> 10 k Ω) where lead resistance is negligible.

5.3 Compliance Settings

Current compliance prevents device damage during voltage sourcing:

$$I_{\text{compliance}} \geq I_{\text{expected,max}} \times 1.2 \quad (9)$$

Set compliance 20% above expected maximum current.

5.4 Timeout Configuration

Timeout prevents software lockup during long measurements:

$$t_{\text{timeout}} = N_{\text{points}} \times \text{NPLC} \times \frac{1}{f_{\text{line}}} \times 3 \quad (10)$$

The software automatically calculates timeout with $3\times$ safety margin. Increase timeout manually for autorange or complex sequences.

6 Standard Characterisation Protocols

6.1 General Measurement Sequence

All protocols follow this base structure:

1. **Initialise:** Measure baseline conductance G_0 (zero illumination). Be sure that the baseline is almost flat at the chosen read voltage, to make sure that the read voltage does not (significantly) contribute to the plasticity. It is almost unavoidable that reading disrupt the system, but we should keep the disruption as small as possible compared to the stimulation.
2. **Stimulate:** Apply optical pulse sequence.
3. **Read:** Measure conductance after each pulse: apply V_{read} , measure I , compute $G = I/V_{\text{read}}$.
4. **Analyse:** Calculate plasticity metrics (see equations below).

Read voltage: We recommend to use $V_{\text{read}} = 0.05\text{--}0.2$ V (non-destructive, linear regime) when using thin film photodiodes. Verify device IV characteristics first, and as previously said, be sure that it does not significantly contribute to the plasticity.

6.2 Long-Term Potentiation (LTP)

Objective: Demonstrate sustained conductance increase under repeated optical stimulation.

Protocol:

1. Measure G_0 (initial conductance, dark conditions).
2. Apply $N = 50\text{--}200$ optical pulses:
 - Pulse intensity: $P_d = 1\text{--}10$ mW cm⁻²
 - Pulse width: $t_{\text{pulse}} = 50\text{--}500$ ms
 - Period: $T = 200\text{--}1000$ ms
3. After each pulse: wait t_{delay} , measure G_n .
4. Plot G_n vs. pulse number n .

Metrics:

$$\Delta G_{\text{LTP}} = G_N - G_0 \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta G_{\%} = \frac{G_N - G_0}{G_0} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

Expected behavior: G_n increases and saturates at G_{max} .

Interpretation of Synaptic Weight. The conductance evolution during LTP is actually an *analogue* modification of the device state. The gradual increase of G_n toward G_{\max} comes from the progressive occupation of metastable defect or trap states, rather than from a discrete ON/OFF transition as we are used to in digital electronics. Each optical pulse slightly changes the population of these traps, and the measured conductance is the cumulative result of those many microscopic contributions. Consequently, the “synaptic weight” is a continuous variable governed by the pulse parameters and the relaxation dynamics of trapped carriers. When reporting potentiation or depression, the weight change should therefore be expressed as a relative conductance variation ($\Delta G/G_0$) and discussed in terms of its analogue and cumulative nature.

6.3 Long-Term Depression (LTD)

Objective: Demonstrate conductance decrease. It often requires reverse bias or dark relaxation, but in some cases, we have observed depression assisted by light (which is ideal, as you then have a fully optically controlled synapse).

Protocol (dark relaxation):

1. Potentiate device to G_{\max} (apply LTP sequence).
2. Measure conductance decay in dark: sample $G(t)$ at intervals (e.g., every 10 s for 10 min).
3. Fit decay: $G(t) = G_{\infty} + (G_{\max} - G_{\infty})e^{-t/\tau}$

Protocol (electrical reset):

1. After LTP, apply negative voltage pulses (if applicable) or opposite polarity.
2. Monitor G_n decrease over M reset pulses.

Metrics:

$$\Delta G_{LTD} = G_0 - G_M \quad (13)$$

$$\tau : \text{decay time constant} \quad (14)$$

Analogue nature of depression. Similar to potentiation, the observed conductance decrease during LTD represents an *analogue* relaxation process rather than a discrete switching event. The reduction of G_n results from the progressive release or recombination of trapped carriers within the device, which leads to a continuous adjustment of the synaptic weight. This analogue interpretation ensures that potentiation and depression are treated as complementary phenomena of the same trap-mediated dynamics governing the device plasticity.

6.4 Short-Term Plasticity: Paired-Pulse Facilitation (PPF)

Objective: Measure conductance enhancement from closely-spaced pulse pairs.

Protocol:

1. Apply two identical optical pulses separated by interval $\Delta t = 10\text{--}100$ ms.
2. Measure G_1 after first pulse, G_2 after second pulse.
3. Repeat for multiple Δt values (e.g., 10, 20, 50, 100 ms).
4. Allow relaxation between trials (~ 60 s in dark).

Metrics:

$$\text{PPF}(\Delta t) = \frac{G_2}{G_1} \times 100\% \quad (15)$$

Expected behavior: $\text{PPF} > 100\%$ for $\Delta t < \tau_{\text{relax}}$, where τ_{relax} is the conductance relaxation time constant.

6.5 Spike-Rate-Dependent Plasticity (SRDP)

Objective: Characterise synaptic weight change as a function of input frequency.

Protocol:

1. Define frequency range: $f_{\min} = 1\text{--}10$ Hz, $f_{\max} = 50\text{--}500$ Hz.
2. Use $N_f = 8\text{--}15$ logarithmically-spaced frequencies:

$$f_i = f_{\min} \cdot \left(\frac{f_{\max}}{f_{\min}} \right)^{i/(N_f-1)}, \quad i = 0, \dots, N_f - 1 \quad (16)$$

3. At each f_i :
 - Measure G_0 .
 - Apply $N_{\text{pulse}} = 30\text{--}100$ pulses at frequency f_i (period $T = 1/f_i$).
 - Measure final conductance G_f .
 - Calculate $\Delta G(f_i) = G_f - G_0$.
 - Allow full relaxation (5–10 min dark) before next frequency.

4. Plot ΔG vs. f .

Typical pulse parameters:

- $t_{\text{pulse}} = 10\text{--}50$ ms (constrain: $t_{\text{pulse}} < T/2$)
- Fixed intensity across all frequencies

Expected behavior: ΔG increases with f (potentiation regime) or decreases (depression regime), possibly showing critical frequency transition.

6.5.1 Modified Approach for AWG + DMM

For SRDP with the AWG + DMM configuration, we need to measure initial and final conductance around each frequency test.

SRDP Step-by-Step Procedure

For each frequency f_i in sweep:

1. Measure initial conductance

- **Electrical:** Set AWG CH1 = 0 V (off)
- **Visual:** Keep LED off (AWG CH1 = 0 V)
- Set AWG CH2 = V_{read} (e.g., 0.1 V)
- Wait 5 seconds for stabilisation
- Measure with DMM: $V_0 = \text{dmm.query('READ?')}$
- Calculate: $G_0 = \frac{V_0}{R_{\text{shunt}} \times V_{\text{read}}}$

2. Configure AWG for frequency f_i

- CH1 pulse period: $t_{\text{period}} = 1/f_i$
- CH1 pulse width: t_{width} (ensure $t_{\text{width}} < t_{\text{period}} - t_{\text{delay}} - 10$ ms)
- **Electrical:** CH1 amplitude = V_{stim} (e.g., +1.0 V for LTP)
- **Visual:** CH1 amplitude = 3.3–5 V (TTL for LED trigger)
- Number of pulses: N (e.g., 50)
- CH2: Maintain $V_{\text{read}} = 0.1$ V

3. Apply stimulus

- Trigger AWG burst
- Wait for completion: `time.sleep(N * t_period + 2)`

4. Measure final conductance

- Wait 5 seconds for device stabilisation
- Set AWG CH1 = 0 V (turn off stimulus/LED)
- Measure: $V_f = \text{dmm.query('READ?')}$
- Calculate: $G_f = \frac{V_f}{R_{\text{shunt}} \times V_{\text{read}}}$

5. Calculate and store

$$\Delta G_{\%} = \frac{G_f - G_0}{G_0} \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

6. Recovery period

- Wait 10–30 seconds before next frequency
- Optional: Apply reset pulses if device supports

Frequency sweep strategy:

- Use logarithmic spacing for wide frequency ranges
- Example: $f = [1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100]$ Hz
- Typical range: 1 Hz to 100 Hz (depending on device time constants)

Frequency Limits

The maximum testable frequency is constrained by:

$$f_{\max} = \frac{1}{t_{\text{width}} + t_{\text{delay}} + t_{\text{measure}} + t_{\text{margin}}} \quad (18)$$

where $t_{\text{measure}} \approx 10$ ms (DMM read time with NPLC=0.1) and $t_{\text{margin}} = 10$ ms (safety).

Example: With $t_{\text{width}} = 10$ ms and $t_{\text{delay}} = 10$ ms:

$$f_{\max} = \frac{1}{10 + 10 + 10 + 10} = 25 \text{ Hz} \quad (19)$$

To achieve higher frequencies:

- Reduce t_{width} and t_{delay} (if device allows)
- Use lower NPLC (0.01–0.02) for faster measurements
- Skip intermediate measurements (measure only initial and final conductance)
- Consider using oscilloscope in place of DMM for $f > 100$ Hz

Practical recommendation: For robust measurements with good SNR, stay below $f_{\max}/2$.

6.6 Spike-Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) Characterisation

The spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP) response of the device was evaluated using a hybrid optical–electrical protocol. Optical spikes served as the *presynaptic* stimuli, while electrical spikes acted as the *postsynaptic* events. The relative timing between the two spikes was defined as

$$\Delta t = t_{\text{pre}} - t_{\text{post}},$$

where $\Delta t > 0$ corresponds to the presynaptic (optical) spike preceding the postsynaptic (electrical) one, and $\Delta t < 0$ corresponds to the opposite case. Positive Δt typically results in potentiation (long-term potentiation, LTP), while negative Δt leads to depression (long-term depression, LTD).

Protocol:

- The device was illuminated by a short optical pulse (*pre-spike*) generated by an LED driven by the first channel of the dual-source meter.
- After a controlled delay Δt , a small voltage pulse (*post-spike*) was applied to the photodiode using the second channel.
- The conductance G of the device was read using a low-amplitude voltage pulse ($V_{\text{read}} \approx 0.1$ – 0.2 V) applied after each spike pair, following a relaxation delay of 10–50 ms to avoid mixing transient photocurrent with the persistent photoconductivity state.
- The timing interval Δt was swept from -50 ms to $+50$ ms in 5 ms steps, limited by the instrument trigger precision.
- Each timing condition was repeated 50 times to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio of the cumulative conductance change $\Delta G = G_{\text{after}} - G_{\text{before}}$.

The STDP learning window was obtained by plotting $\Delta G/G_0$ as a function of Δt . The resulting curve was fitted with the conventional exponential learning rule:

$$\Delta G(\Delta t) = \begin{cases} A_+ e^{-\Delta t/\tau_+}, & \Delta t > 0, \\ -A_- e^{\Delta t/\tau_-}, & \Delta t < 0, \end{cases}$$

where A_+ and A_- are the maximum amplitudes of potentiation and depression, and τ_+ and τ_- are the respective characteristic time constants.

Physical interpretation: In this configuration, the optical spike controls the generation of photocarriers and their capture into metastable traps, while the electrical post-spike perturbs the trapped charge population through field-assisted detrapping. When the pre-spike precedes the post-spike ($\Delta t > 0$), the field enhances the stabilization of photogenerated carriers, leading to potentiation. Conversely, when the post-spike occurs before the pre-spike ($\Delta t < 0$), the field acts on an unexcited trap population, favoring carrier extraction and conductance depression.

Fully optical STDP variant: For devices exhibiting wavelength-selective behavior, where one wavelength (λ_1) induces potentiation and another (λ_2) induces depression, a fully optical STDP protocol was also implemented:

1. Apply an optical pair of pulses: λ_1 (pre) and λ_2 (post) for $\Delta t > 0$, or the reverse order for $\Delta t < 0$.
2. Sweep Δt as above, and measure the persistent conductance change after each pair.
3. Plot $\Delta G(\Delta t)$ and fit with the same exponential model.

Before the STDP measurement, each wavelength's individual effect on conductance was characterised separately to isolate cross-sensitivity between potentiating and depressing channels.

Quantitative metric: An asymmetry index was defined to quantify the degree of biological-like learning:

$$A_{\text{STDP}} = \frac{A_+ - A_-}{A_+ + A_-}.$$

A perfectly symmetric response yields $A_{\text{STDP}} = 0$, while larger positive (or negative) values indicate dominant potentiation (or depression) behavior.

This hybrid or fully optical STDP protocol captures the dynamic interplay between trap occupation, photoexcitation, and field-assisted relaxation, allowing direct emulation of Hebbian learning rules in light-sensitive artificial synapses.

6.6.1 Implementation Notes for AWG + DMM

For Electrical Synapses:

- Pre-spike: Voltage pulse on AWG Ch1
- Post-spike: Voltage pulse on AWG Ch2
- Both channels deliver electrical pulses to different device terminals

For Visual Synapses:

- Pre-spike: Optical pulse (AWG Ch1 triggers LED)
- Post-spike: Electrical pulse (AWG Ch2 applies voltage to device)

- Mixed optical-electrical protocol

AWG Channel Synchronisation

Critical Requirement: Both AWG channels must be synchronised to nanosecond precision!

- Check your AWG specifications for inter-channel skew
- Most modern AWGs provide < 1 ns skew between channels
- Use AWG's internal trigger/sync to start both channels simultaneously
- Verify sync with oscilloscope before running experiments
- Some AWGs have “coupled” or “synchronised” channel modes – use these!

6.7 Potentiation-Depression Cycling

6.7.1 Measurement Principle

Cycling tests device endurance by alternating between potentiation (positive stimulus) and depression (negative stimulus) phases.

Electrical Synapses:

- Potentiation: Apply positive voltage pulses ($+V_{\text{pot}}$)
- Depression: Apply negative voltage pulses ($-V_{\text{dep}}$)

Visual Synapses:

- Potentiation: Apply optical pulses (high intensity or longer duration)
- Depression: Either dark relaxation, or optical pulses with reverse electrical bias
- Some materials show optical depression (light-assisted conductance decrease)

Cycling Step-by-Step Procedure

For each cycle $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{cycles}}$:

1. Potentiation Phase

- Configure AWG CH1: Amplitude $+V_{\text{pot}}$ (electrical) or TTL (visual), Width $t_{\text{pot,width}}$ (e.g., 100 ms), Period $t_{\text{pot,period}}$ (e.g., 200 ms), Count N_{pot} (e.g., 50)
- Configure AWG CH2: $V_{\text{read}} = 0.1$ V (constant)
- **Measure:** After each pulse or only endpoints
- Trigger AWG burst and wait for completion
- Calculate: $\Delta G_{\text{pot}} = G_{\text{final}} - G_{\text{initial}}$

2. **Inter-phase delay:** Wait 0.5–2 seconds

3. Depression Phase

- **Electrical:** Configure AWG CH1 with $-V_{\text{dep}}$
- **Visual:** Either dark relaxation (measure decay over time) or optical pulses with reverse bias
- Measure conductance evolution
- Calculate: $\Delta G_{\text{dep}} = G_{\text{final}} - G_{\text{initial}}$

4. **Inter-cycle delay:** Wait 1–5 seconds

5. **Record cycle data:** Cycle number, Potentiation $\Delta G_{\%}$, Depression $\Delta G_{\%}$, Final conductances

Post-processing metrics:

- Mean potentiation/depression ΔG
- Reproducibility (coefficient of variation): $CV = \frac{\sigma(\Delta G)}{|\mu(\Delta G)|} \times 100\%$
- Dynamic range: $\langle G_{\text{pot,final}} \rangle - \langle G_{\text{dep,final}} \rangle$
- On/off ratio: $\frac{\langle G_{\text{pot,final}} \rangle}{\langle G_{\text{dep,final}} \rangle}$

6.8 Current-Voltage (JV) Hysteresis

Objective: Characterise memristive behavior in the device electrical response.

Protocol:

1. Dark sweep:

- Sweep voltage: $V = -0.2$ to $+1.0$ V (forward), then reverse (backward).
- Step size: $\Delta V = 10$ – 20 mV.
- Measure current at each point.

2. Illuminated sweep:

- Apply constant illumination ($P_d = 1$ – 10 mW cm⁻²).
- Repeat forward-backward voltage sweep.

3. Light-soaking effect:

- Pre-illuminate device (e.g., 60 s at 10 mW cm^{-2}).
- Immediately measure dark JV curve.
- Compare with initial dark JV (measure hysteresis width).

Analysis:

- Hysteresis area: $A_{\text{hyst}} = \oint I dV$
- Shift in turn-on voltage or resistance state between forward/backward sweeps
- Persistence of conductance change after light removal

7 Data Acquisition and Analysis

7.1 Data Structure

Record for each measurement:

- Time stamp (relative to sequence start)
 - Pulse index n
 - Measured current I [A]
 - Applied read voltage V_{read} [V]
 - Calculated conductance $G = I/V_{\text{read}}$ [S]
 - Optical parameters: λ , P_d , t_{pulse}
 - Environmental conditions: temperature, ambient light (if not in dark box)
- Metadata:** Device ID, area, materials, measurement date, protocol parameters.

7.2 Key Metrics

Metric	Definition	Interpretation
ΔG	$G_f - G_i$	Absolute conductance change
$\Delta G\%$	$(G_f - G_i)/G_i \times 100\%$	Relative change
Dynamic range	$G_{\text{max}}/G_{\text{min}}$	On/off ratio
PPF	$G_2/G_1 \times 100\%$	Short-term facilitation
Nonlinearity	Deviation from linear $G(n)$	Synaptic update symmetry

Table 4: Synaptic plasticity metrics

7.3 Typical Results

LTP: Expect $\Delta G > 20\text{--}100\%$ over 50–200 pulses. Saturation indicates G_{max} reached.

SRDP: Logarithmic or sigmoidal $\Delta G(f)$ relationship. Critical frequency f_c marks LTD-to-LTP transition.

STDP: Asymmetric window with $\Delta G > 0$ for $\Delta t > 0$ and $\Delta G < 0$ for $\Delta t < 0$. Time constants $\tau_{\pm} = 10\text{--}50$ ms typical.

JV Hysteresis: Pinched loop at origin indicates memristive behavior. Hysteresis width correlates with memory retention.

8 Calibration and Validation

8.1 Shunt Resistor Calibration

Before experiments, verify R_{shunt} value:

1. Use precision LCR metre or DMM in 4-wire mode
2. Measure at operating temperature
3. Record: $R_{\text{shunt,actual}} = \underline{\hspace{2cm}} \Omega$
4. Use this value in all calculations

8.2 System Validation

Test with known resistor before measuring devices:

1. Replace synapse device with precision resistor ($R_{\text{test}} = 10 \text{ k}\Omega \pm 0.1\%$)
2. Apply $V_{\text{read}} = 0.1 \text{ V}$ from AWG CH2
3. Measure voltage across shunt with DMM
4. Calculate conductance: $G_{\text{measured}} = \frac{V_{\text{DMM}}}{R_{\text{shunt}} \times V_{\text{read}}}$
5. Expected: $G_{\text{expected}} = 1/R_{\text{test}} = 100 \mu\text{S}$
6. Error should be $< 1\%$

8.3 Optical Calibration Verification (Visual Synapses)

1. Position power metre at device location
2. Trigger LED with AWG CH1 (TTL pulse)
3. Measure optical power: P_{opt} [mW]
4. Measure beam diameter: d [mm]
5. Calculate power density: $P_d = \frac{4P_{\text{opt}}}{\pi d^2}$ [mW cm⁻²]
6. Verify uniformity across device area
7. Document: wavelength, power, LED current, distance

8.4 Noise Assessment

Characterise system noise floor:

1. Short DMM input terminals (0 V)
2. Record 1000 measurements over 10 seconds
3. Calculate RMS noise: $V_{\text{noise,RMS}}$
4. This defines minimum detectable ΔG :

$$G_{\text{min}} = \frac{V_{\text{noise,RMS}}}{R_{\text{shunt}} \times V_{\text{read}}} \times 3 \quad (20)$$

9 Experimental Best Practices

9.1 Device Considerations

- **Compliance:** Set current compliance 20% above expected maximum to prevent device damage.
- **Bias polarity:** Verify device polarity (some devices require specific bias direction for potentiation).
- **Active area:** Define and document device illuminated area for power density calculations.
- **4-wire vs. 2-wire:** Use 4-wire (Kelvin) sensing for low-resistance devices ($< 100 \Omega$).

9.2 Environmental Control

- **Dark box:** Essential. Eliminate ambient light during measurements.
- **Temperature:** Ideally it should be monitored and stable, as we are measuring very small currents. Ideally...
- **Humidity:** Can be important for air-sensitive materials, but has not been an issue for us so far.

Measurement quality

- **Repeatability:** We should try to perform measurements per protocol and report mean \pm standard deviation. But some devices may degrade.
- **Relaxation time:** Allow sufficient dark recovery between measurements (typically 5–10 min) to avoid cumulative effects. If you have a way to reset the device, optically or electrically, even better.
- **Baseline stability:** Verify G_0 returns to initial value after relaxation. If not, device may show fatigue or irreversible damages.
- **Cable shielding:** If doing very low current measurements, we recommend shielded coaxial cables to minimise electromagnetic interference.

9.3 Multi-Device Sequential Testing

For testing multiple devices with the same protocol:

Multi-Device Workflow

1. Device connection

- Use probe station or switching matrix to connect different devices
- Manual switching: Move probes between devices
- Automated switching: Use relay matrix (if available)

2. For each device

- Verify electrical connection (measure DC resistance)
- Run selected characterisation protocol (Basic/SRDP/STDP/Cycling)
- Save data with device identifier
- Disconnect device

3. Statistical analysis

- Compare ΔG distributions across devices
- Identify outliers
- Calculate device-to-device variability

10 Software Integration

In the frame of the project SOLIS, we developed the SOLIS control software (see separate User Manual, SOLIS-Sourcemeter v1.0) which implements these protocols for Keithley 2636A systems. For Configuration B setups, adapt the software control logic:

Required modifications:

- Replace Keithley VISA commands with WFG-specific commands (SCPI standard for most instruments).
- Implement external triggering: send trigger signal to DMM after $t_{\text{pulse}} + t_{\text{delay}}$.
- Read current from DMM via VISA/GPIB/USB after each trigger.
- Calculate conductance: $G = I_{\text{DMM}}/V_{\text{read, WFG}}$.

Example Python pseudocode (Configuration B, fully automated):

```
import pyvisa
rm = pyvisa.ResourceManager()
wfg = rm.open_resource('USB::0x1234::0x5678::INSTR') # WFG address
dmm = rm.open_resource('USB::0xABCD::0xEF01::INSTR') # DMM address

# Configure WFG
wfg.write('SOURCE1:FUNCTION PULSE') # Ch1: LED trigger
wfg.write(f'SOURCE1:PULSE:WIDTH {t_pulse}')
wfg.write(f'SOURCE1:VOLTAGE:HIGH 3.3') # TTL level
wfg.write('SOURCE2:VOLTAGE:LEVEL {V_read}') # Ch2: read voltage

# Configure DMM
dmm.write('TRIGGER:SOURCE EXTERNAL')
dmm.write(f'TRIGGER:DELAY {t_delay + t_settle}')
```

```
for n in range(N_pulses):
    wfg.write('TRIGger') # Trigger WFG (outputs Ch1 pulse, maintains Ch2)
    dmm.write('INITiate') # Arm DMM for triggered measurement
    I = float(dmm.query('FETCh?')) # Read current
    G = I / V_read
    # Store data: n, I, G
    time.sleep(T_period) # Wait for next pulse
```

11 Summary and Recommendations

11.1 Minimum Equipment Requirements

- **Configuration A:** Dual-channel SMU (e.g., Keithley 2636A), fiber-coupled LED, triggered driver, optical components. Cost: $\sim\text{€}15,000$.
- **Configuration B:** Dual-channel WFG, triggerable DMM, fiber-coupled LED, triggered driver, optical components. Cost: $\sim\text{€}2,350$.
- **Custom-made** At UPC, we use a more advanced sourcemeter (Keysight B1500A) which costs an arm and a leg, but permits timescales of ns and a current resolution of 10nA with the proper module. One can always adapt those guidelines to their available setup, of course. The University of Liverpool also has a custom setup.

11.2 Critical Success Factors

1. **Optical calibration:** Accurate P_d measurement is essential for reproducibility. Really be sure that you know your incident power.
2. **Timing synchronisation:** Verify trigger delays and instrument response times. You don't want the measure to occur after the read voltage pulse, for example. We recommend starting slow, and progressively increasing the speed (e.g. decreasing the timescales).
3. **NPLC optimization:** Balance measurement speed vs. noise based on device dynamics.
4. **Environmental stability:** Dark box is really essential, and maybe temperature/humidity control, shielded cables.
5. **Systematic protocols:** As much as possible, we should try to follow standardised sequences for cross-lab comparisons.

11.3 Recommended Workflow

1. **Initial characterisation:** Dark and illuminated JV curves to identify memristive behavior and select V_{read} .
2. **Basic plasticity:** LTP/LTD to verify synaptic response and determine optimal pulse parameters.
3. **Advanced protocols:** PPF, SRDP, STDP to fully characterise plasticity functions.
4. **Wavelength dependence:** Repeat key protocols with multiple LEDs (if device is wavelength-selective).
5. **Endurance testing:** Potentiation-depression cycling (100–1000 cycles) for stability assessment.

12 Conclusion

This guide provides a practical framework specifically addressed to thin film PV researchers to establish visual synapse characterisation capabilities using accessible equipment. The described protocols form a standardised basis for comparing results across the SOLIS consortium and the broader research community.

For detailed software implementation, refer to the *Source meter User Manual for Keithley 2636A* (SOLIS Project, v1.0). Adapt the provided Python control framework to your specific instrumentation following the synchronisation principles outlined in Section 4.

13 Appendix A: Equipment Specifications

13.1 Waveform Generator Requirements

Minimum specifications:

- Dual-channel output
- Frequency range: DC to 1 MHz (sufficient for ms-scale pulses)
- Output voltage: 0–5 V (for LED driver triggering and device biasing)
- Pulse generation capability with adjustable width and period
- Trigger output (TTL-compatible) for synchronizing external instruments
- VISA/SCPI command interface (USB, GPIB, or Ethernet)

Recommended: Multicomp Pro MP751062

- 2 channels, 60 MHz bandwidth
- Arbitrary waveform generation
- External trigger input/output
- USB and LAN connectivity
- Cost: ~€250

13.2 Digital Multimeter Requirements

Minimum specifications:

- Current measurement range: nA to mA (device-dependent)
- 5.5–6.5 digit resolution
- External trigger input capability
- Measurement speed: < 10 ms per reading (at reduced NPLC)
- VISA/SCPI programmable interface

Recommended: Keysight 34460A

- 6.5-digit Truevolt DMM
- 1 nA to 10 A range
- External trigger support
- NPLC: 0.02–100
- USB, GPIB, LAN interfaces
- Cost: ~€1,300

Alternative: Single-channel Source meter (e.g., Keithley 2400, 2450) can replace the DMM, providing both voltage sourcing and current measurement with better integration. But you are still going to need at least a single channel waveform generator for the illumination, and to trigger the application of the read voltage and current measurement by the sourcemeter.

13.3 LED and Driver Specifications

Fiber-coupled LED requirements:

- Wavelengths: 365–1500 nm (select based on device absorption; subgap defects can also be probed by low energy LEDs)
- Optical power: 1–50 mW (fiber-coupled)
- SMA or FC/PC fiber connector
- Spectral width: 10–50 nm (typical for LEDs)

Recommended wavelengths for thin film synapses:

- 430 nm (blue): CdTe, kesterite, Sb_2S_3 absorption
- 530 nm (green): Broader absorption range
- 625 nm (red): Near bandgap excitation for wider-gap materials
- 850 nm and above (IR): Sub-bandgap excitation, defect-mediated absorption

LED driver requirements:

- External trigger input (TTL, 3.3–5 V)
- Trigger-to-output delay: $< 1 \mu\text{s}$
- Constant current drive mode
- Current range: 100–1000 mA (LED-dependent)

Recommended: Thorlabs LEDD1B T-Cube

- External trigger input (BNC)
- 1200 mA maximum current
- Modulation bandwidth: DC to 500 kHz
- Cost: $\sim \text{€}350$

13.4 Optical Components

Optical fiber:

- Multimode fiber, 200–600 μm core diameter
- SMA-SMA or FC/PC-FC/PC connectors
- Length: 1–2 m (sufficient for most setups)
- Cost: $\sim \text{€}50\text{--}100$

Collimator/focusing optics:

- SMA-threaded collimation package
- Focal length: 11–25 mm (adjustable spot size)
- Optical mount for positioning
- Cost: $\sim \text{€}100\text{--}150$

Optical power meter:

- Si photodiode detector (350–1100 nm)
- Power range: 1 nW to 100 mW
- Calibration certificate (traceable)
- Cost: $\sim \text{€}500\text{--}1,500$

14 Appendix B: Timing Diagram Examples

14.1 Configuration A: Keithley 2636A

Time axis (ms):

Channel B (LED trigger):

```
|#####|-----| (50 ms pulse)
```

LED output:

```
|#####|-----| (50 ms illumination)
```

Wait periods:

```
 |--t_delay--|--t_settle--|
 (50 ms)      (10 ms)
```

Channel A (read voltage):

```
|#####|-----| (V_read ON, measure I)
```

Current measurement:

```
|#| (NPLC=1, ~17 ms)
```

Period: 200 ms

14.2 Configuration B: WFG + DMM (ASCII)

Time axis (ms):

```
|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
0      50    100   150   200   250   300   350   400
```

WFG Ch1 (LED trigger):

```
|#####|-----| (50 ms TTL pulse)
```

LED output:

```
|#####|-----| (50 ms illumination)
```

WFG Ch2 (V_read):

```
|#####_| (constant bias)
```

DMM trigger signal:

```
|#|-----| (trigger at t=100 ms)
```

DMM measurement:

```
|#####|-----| (acquire after t_delay+t_settle)
```

Period: 200 ms

Note: Trigger delays must be calibrated for your specific instruments. Use oscilloscope to verify timing if discrepancies occur.

14.3 Configuration B: WFG + DMM (TikZ)

15 Appendix C: Sample Data Analysis

15.1 Conductance Calculation

Raw data from each pulse:

$$I_n : \text{measured current after pulse } n \text{ [A]} \quad (21)$$

$$V_{\text{read}} : \text{applied read voltage [V]} \quad (22)$$

$$G_n = \frac{I_n}{V_{\text{read}}} \text{ [S]} \quad (23)$$

Units:

- Siemens (S) = Ω^{-1}
- Typical range: nS to μS for thin film devices
- Conversion: 1 nS = 10^{-9} S, 1 μS = 10^{-6} S

15.2 Plasticity Metrics Example

LTP measurement data (example):

- Initial conductance: $G_0 = 50$ nS
- Final conductance (after 100 pulses): $G_{100} = 85$ nS

Calculated metrics:

$$\Delta G = 85 - 50 = 35 \text{ nS} \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta G\% = \frac{85 - 50}{50} \times 100\% = 70\% \quad (25)$$

$$\text{Dynamic range} = \frac{G_{\text{max}}}{G_{\text{min}}} = \frac{85}{50} = 1.7 \text{ (or 70\% increase)} \quad (26)$$

Frequency [Hz]	G_0 [nS]	G_f [nS]	ΔG [nS]
1	50	52	+2
2.5	50	55	+5
5	50	62	+12
10	50	73	+23
25	50	82	+32
50	50	87	+37
100	50	89	+39

Table 5: Example SRDP measurement (100 pulses per frequency)

15.3 SRDP Analysis Example

Measured data:

Interpretation: ΔG increases logarithmically with frequency, saturating above 50 Hz. Critical frequency for substantial potentiation: $f_c \approx 5\text{--}10$ Hz.

15.4 STDP Analysis Example

Expected fit parameters:

- Potentiation amplitude: $A_+ = 30\text{--}40$ nS
- Depression amplitude: $A_- = 15\text{--}25$ nS
- Time constants: $\tau_+ = \tau_- = 15\text{--}25$ ms

Asymmetry index:

$$AI = \frac{A_+}{A_-} \quad (27)$$

Typical range: $AI = 1.5\text{--}2.5$ (potentiation stronger than depression).

16 Appendix D: Quick Reference Tables

16.1 Typical Protocol Parameters

Protocol	t_{pulse} [ms]	Period [ms]	N_{pulses}	P_d [mW/cm ²]
LTP	50–500	200–1000	50–200	1–10
LTD (dark)	—	—	—	0 (measure decay)
PPF	10–50	20–100	2 (pair)	5–20
SRDP	10–50	$1/f$	30–100 per f	5–10
STDP	10–20	200–500	30–100 pairs	5–15
JV hysteresis	—	—	—	0 or 1–10

Table 6: Recommended starting parameters for each protocol

16.2 Read Voltage Selection

Note: Always verify that V_{read} is in the linear (ohmic) regime of the device IV curve.

16.3 Instrument Settings Summary

Keithley 2636A:

Device Resistance	V_{read} [V]	Expected I range
$< 1 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.05–0.1	50–100 μA
1–100 $\text{k}\Omega$	0.1–0.2	1–100 μA
$> 100 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.2–0.5	10–1000 nA

Table 7: Read voltage selection guidelines (verify linear regime first)

- NPLC: 0.1–1
- Autorange: OFF (set fixed range based on expected current)
- Compliance: $1.2 \times I_{\text{max}}$ (expected maximum current)
- 4-wire sensing: ON (for $R < 100 \Omega$)

DMM (e.g., Keysight 34460A):

- Function: DC current measurement
- Range: Auto or fixed (nA to mA, device-dependent)
- NPLC: 0.1–1 (fast mode)
- Trigger: External, edge-triggered
- Trigger delay: $t_{\text{delay}} + t_{\text{settle}}$

Waveform generator:

- Ch1: Pulse function, amplitude 3.3–5 V (TTL), width t_{pulse} , period T
- Ch2: DC function, amplitude V_{read}
- Trigger mode: Continuous or single (protocol-dependent)

16.4 Comparison: Electrical vs Visual Synapses

Aspect	Electrical	Visual/Optical
Stimulus type	Voltage/current pulses	Optical pulses (LED)
AWG CH1 function	Device stimulus	LED trigger (TTL)
Device types	Memristors, ReRAM, PCM	Photovoltaic, photoconductive
Calibration	Electrical only	Electrical + optical power
Complexity	Moderate	Higher (optical path)
Additional cost	€0	€600–800 (LED + driver)
Speed capability	Very fast ($< 1 \text{ ms}$)	Limited by LED driver
Wavelength effects	N/A	Material-dependent

Table 8: Comparison between electrical and optical synapse characterisation

16.5 Comparison: Sourcemeter vs AWG+DMM

17 Appendix E: Material-Specific Considerations

17.1 Common Thin Film PV Materials

CdTe:

- Bandgap: 1.45 eV ($\lambda < 850 \text{ nm}$)
- Recommended LED: 430–625 nm
- Known metastability: Light soaking improves fill factor (Cu migration)
- Expected synaptic behavior: Moderate LTP, strong persistence

CIGS/Kesterite (CZTS):

Aspect	Dual Sourcemeter	AWG + DMM
Computer control	Full (both channels)	Partial (DMM only)
Synchronisation	Automatic	Manual or external trigger
Measurement speed	Fast (< 1 ms/point)	Moderate (10–50 ms/point)
Setup complexity	Low	Moderate
Cost	High (€12k–25k)	Lower (€1.2k–3.7k)
Flexibility	High	Moderate
Required expertise	Moderate	Higher
Visual synapse support	Requires LED + driver	Built-in (LED trigger)

Table 9: Comparison between sourcemeter and AWG+DMM approaches

- Bandgap: 1.0–1.5 eV (tunable with Ga or composition)
 - Recommended LED: 530–850 nm
 - Known metastability: V_{OC} increase under light soaking (defect reordering)
 - Expected synaptic behavior: Strong LTP/LTD, good dynamic range
- Sb₂S₃/Sb₂Se₃:**
- Bandgap: 1.1–1.7 eV (S vs. Se)
 - Recommended LED: 430–730 nm
 - Known metastability: Interface defects, persistent photoconductivity
 - Expected synaptic behavior: Fast response, wavelength-selective
- Perovskite (CH₃NH₃PbI₃):**
- Bandgap: 1.55 eV
 - Recommended LED: 530–730 nm
 - Known metastability: Ion migration, strong hysteresis
 - Expected synaptic behavior: Very strong memristive behavior, but stability concerns
 - *Caution:* Measure in inert atmosphere or encapsulated devices

17.2 Wavelength-Dependent Response

For materials with strong absorption edge, synaptic response varies with wavelength:

Above bandgap ($h\nu > E_g$):

- Strong absorption, high carrier generation
- Fast conductance increase (strong LTP)
- May saturate quickly

Near bandgap ($h\nu \approx E_g$):

- Moderate absorption
- Balanced LTP/LTD dynamics
- Optimal for SRDP/STDP characterisation

Below bandgap ($h\nu < E_g$):

- Defect-mediated absorption
- Slow, persistent conductance change
- Long time constants (suitable for memory applications)

Recommendation: Characterise with 2–3 wavelengths spanning above/near/below bandgap.

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Companion Software: The SOLIS characterisation software (Python-based, open-source) is available at:

<https://github.com/SOLIS-project/Keithley-2636A-Parameter-analyser>

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